

Notes

Spectroscopic Studies of some New Diorganotin(IV)- β -diketonate Complexes

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METAL- β -diketonato complexes of metals have been studied both experimentally¹⁻⁵ and theoretically. Most of the experimental studies have been carried out to investigate differences in the spectra with change of metal atom and to find out their coordination behaviour. Some tin- β -diketonato complexes of the type $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{AcAc})_2$ have been investigated in great detail⁶⁻¹⁰.

The present paper reports the synthesis and spectroscopic investigations of some diaryltin-bis(acetylacetonates) of the type $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{AcAc})_2$ ($\text{AcAc}=\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_3$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5$). These complexes have been characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis, conductance measurements, ir and ¹H nmr spectral studies.

Experimental

All the required organic solvents, such as benzene, petroleum ether, acetone, acetyl acetone, benzoyl acetone and dibenzoylmethane were purified and dried before use by the well known standard methods. Nitrobenzene for conductance measurements was purified as described by Fay and Lowry¹⁴. Sodium methoxide was prepared by the interaction of sodium metal with methanol. Bis(*p*-biphenyl)tin dichloride was prepared as given in the literature¹⁵.

Bis(p-biphenyltin)-bis(acetylacetonate): To a mixture of bis(*p*-biphenyl)tin dichloride (0.9914 g,

2 mmol) in methanol (0 ml) was added sodium metal (0.5 g) and acetylacetone (0.4 g, 4 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 1.5 h and the precipitate of sodium chloride was filtered. The filtrate was reduced under vacuum to 10 ml and then petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) was added dropwise with constant shaking till the precipitation was complete. A white compound was obtained which on recrystallisation from benzene gave a white crystalline solid corresponding to the formula $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2$ (75%). The other acetylacetonates of bis(*p*-biphenyl)tin dichloride were prepared by the same procedure. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets in 4 000-400 cm^{-1} region. Pmr spectra were recorded at ambient temperature (28°) at a sweep-width of 900 Hz with a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer. The spectra were recorded in triplicate and the average values considered. The magnetic field sweep was calibrated with standard sample of chloroform and tetramethyl silane (1%) in deuterated chloroform.

Results and Discussion

The synthesis of organotin-bis(acetylacetonates) may be represented with the following chemical equation.

All the three complexes reported in this paper are crystalline solids with sharp melting points. They are stable in dry atmosphere and soluble in most of the common organic solvents, like acetone, chloroform, benzene, methanol and ethanol but insoluble in petroleum ether. Molecular weight and conductance data in nitrobenzene show that all these complexes are monomeric.

Infrared spectra: Nakamoto *et al.*¹⁶ assigned a strong band $\sim 1\ 630\text{-}1\ 560\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$. Lawson⁴ supported the result experimentally by showing some degree of linear dependence of the frequency

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR BIS(*p*-BIPHENYLTIN(IV)- β -DIKETONE) COMPOUNDS

Compd.*	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	Sn
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2$	110	65.31 (65.57)	4.92 (5.14)	19.40 (19.08)
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_3)_2$	96	70.46 (70.55)	4.76 (4.82)	15.30 (15.90)
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$	82	74.21 (74.43)	4.42 (4.59)	13.23 (13.63)

*All are white solid.

of this band upon the first, second and third ionisation potentials of the metals for mono-, bis- and tris-acetylacetonates, respectively. Lecomte¹ assigned a strong band $\sim 1400-1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu_{\sigma-\sigma}$. McGrady and Tobias¹³ have also studied the diorgano (alkyl and aryl)tinacetylacetonates. According to these workers, with the symmetrical ligands only two geometrical isomers, *cis* and *trans* are possible.

The most interesting characteristic of the ir spectrum of these complexes is that there is only one strong antisymmetric stretching vibration of the Sn—C band at 560 cm^{-1} while there is no-symmetric Sn—C stretching vibration. This will lead to conclude that the two biphenyl groups in these compounds are in the *trans*-position with the central tin atom. The four Sn—O bonds in these acetylacetonates, therefore, seems to be nearly equivalent.

The other absorption bands in these complexes can be assigned as follows. Most of these complexes show two strong bands in the $1500-1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The upper band $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to a perturbed C=O vibration and the lower band $\sim 1540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to a perturbed C=C stretching mode. The spectra in the $1500-1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region are somewhat complicated. All the compounds show four absorption bands. Two bands at ~ 1475 and 1370 cm^{-1} and whose positions are same as in free acetylacetonate molecule, are assigned to CH_2 degenerate and symmetric deformation. Another two bands are $\sim 1390-1310$ and $1280-1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and may be assigned to C—O stretching and C—C stretching, respectively. In the $1200-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, the C—H out-of-plane deformation band in diorganotinacetylacetonates appears at 820 and 755 cm^{-1} which is $20-40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ higher than those in the usual metal-acetylacetonates. In the $700-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region there appear two slightly broad absorption located at ~ 695 and 570 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to antisymmetric and symmetric Sn—O stretching vibrations, respectively.

¹H nmr spectra; The ¹H nmr spectra resonance signals due to biphenyl protons appear in the form of a doublet, a triplet and a doublet between $2-3\tau$. In the complex $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{AcAc})_2$, resonance signal due to the methyl group of acetylacetonate appears as a singlet $\sim 8.0\tau$. In the complex $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{bzAc})_2$, there is a multiplet in the region $2-3\tau$. It is due to the merging of the phenyl proton signals of benzoylacetonate into signals due to protons of biphenyl group. There is a singlet $\sim 7.9\tau$ due to the protons of the methyl group of the benzoyl acetate. In the complex $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{bzAc})_2$, a multiplet in the region $2-3\tau$ is again due to the mixing of the phenyl protons in the biphenyl signals. In all these complexes, there is a signal $\sim 4\tau$ due to CH protons.

In case of $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{AcAc})_2$ and $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{bzAc})_2$, there is only a single singlet $\sim 8.0\tau$ due to methyl protons which

suggests that these complexes are having *trans*-configuration and the biphenyl groups are probably rotating freely¹³. If there would have been *cis*-configuration in these complexes, we should get a doublet for methyl protons as there is only a two-fold axis with the molecule having two sets of two symmetrically equivalent R' groups, whereas in *trans*-configuration all ligand biphenyl groups form a symmetrical equivalent set. Thus, on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and ¹H nmr spectral studies all the complexes have biphenyl groups in *trans*-position and have coordination number six, β -diketone moiety acting as bidentate ligand.

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Metal Complexes as Ligands. Polynuclear Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes with Copper(II)- and Nickel(II)-Salicylaldimines

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IN continuation of our previous work¹, the present study involves the synthesis and characterisation of the complexes formed by Ni²⁺- and Cu²⁺-salicylaldimines with alkaline earth salts of inorganic and organic acids.

Experimental

To a mixture of CuES or NiES in chloroform and absolute ethanol (1:1), was added alkaline